

Effect of Change Proneness on the Psychological Well-Being of the Elderly Women

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Abstract

The present investigation attempts to find out the effect of change proneness on the psychological well-being of the elderly women. The present study was conducted on 120 elderly women from different old age homes and also from residence of Chennai city of which 60 were living with children and 60 were living without children. Out of the 60 elderly women, 30 were from urban area and 30 were from rural area. The same was repeated with the other group also. The tools used for the investigation were Development of Change Proneness Scale by Pratibha Sood and Shalini Bhogle (1997) and Ryff's Psychological well being 18 item (1998). The collected data was tabulated and subjected to statistical analysis using mean, standard deviation, 't'-test and Karl Pearson's Coefficient Correlation.

The results of the present study revealed that women living with family spend more time with friends and they are more socially active. To be a part of the circle they are ready to adapt to changes rather than being rigid. Although minimal difference was found between both the groups change proneness was found to be slightly high among elderly women living with family. Change proneness was found to be more among elderly female staying in rural area than those staying in urban area. This reveals that elderly in rural area are more attached to family and are willing to adapt to change rather than being rigid. Elderly staying in urban area had better psychological well-being than those in rural area as they had better facilities in urban areas. It was also revealed that there was found to be relationship between psychological well-being and change proneness among the elderly female which indicates that more a person is flexible and adapts to change better will be the relationship with family and inturn better will be the psychological well being.

Keywords: Change proneness, Psychological well-being, Elderly women, Locality, place of residence.

Introduction

Ageing is an inevitable developmental phenomenon bringing along a number of changes in the physical, psychological, hormonal and the social conditions. Ageing in terms of the biology; refers to “the regular changes that occur in mature genetically representative organism living under reprehensive environmental conditions as they advance in chronological age.”

Old people are also called “senior citizens” or “elders”. Elders are considered to be wise because they have had much experience in their long lives. Many cultures view elders with respect and kindness,

and depend upon them to pass down knowledge to the younger people. But old age has been also viewed, as problematic period of one's life and this is correct to some extent. The aged become increasingly dependent on others. As man grows, his reduced activities, income and consequent decline in the position of the family and society makes his life more vulnerable.

Change-proneness means inclination or readiness one has to change or alter his behaviour, attitudes, feelings and thoughts by being flexible rather restraining oneself to be rigid (Mukhopadhyaya, 1981).

Psychological Well-being refers to the simple notion of a person's welfare, happiness, advantages, interests, utility and quality of life. (Burris, Brechting, Salsman, & Carlson, 2009).

Psychological well-being consists of positive relationships with others, personal mastery, autonomy, a feeling of purpose and meaning in life, and personal growth and development. Psychological well-being is attained by achieving a state of balance affected by both challenging and rewarding life events. At the most basic level, psychological wellbeing (PWB) is quite similar to other terms that refer to positive mental states, such as happiness or satisfaction, and in many ways it is not necessary, or helpful to worry about fine distinctions between such terms.

Actually, PWB has two important facets. The first of these refers to the extent to which people experience positive emotions and feelings of happiness. Sometimes this aspect of PWB is referred to as subjective wellbeing (Diener, 2000). Subjective wellbeing is a necessary part of overall PWB. So, the two important ingredients in PWB are the subjective happy feelings brought on by something we enjoy and the feeling that what we are doing with our lives has some meaning and purpose. The term "Hedonic" wellbeing is normally used to refer to the subjective feelings of happiness and, the less well-known term, "Eudaimonic" wellbeing is used to refer to the purposeful aspect of PWB. The psychologist Carol Ryff has developed a very clear model that breaks down Eudaimonic wellbeing into six key parts.

Psychological well-being refers to how people evaluate their lives. According to Diener (1997), these evaluations may be in the form of cognitions or in the form of affect. The cognitive part is an information based appraisal of one's life that is when a person gives conscious evaluative judgments about one's satisfaction with life as a whole. The affective part is a hedonic evaluation guided by emotions and feelings such as frequency with which people experience pleasant/unpleasant moods in reaction to their lives. The assumption behind this is that most people evaluate their life as either good or bad, so they are normally able to offer judgments. Further, people invariably experience moods and emotions, which have a positive effect or a negative effect. Thus, people have a level of subjective well-being even if they do not often consciously think about it, and the psychological system offers virtually a constant evaluation of what is happening to the person.

An observation of the reviews on this topic shows that extensive research has been carried out on the effect of psychological well-being on the life of the elderly. Not much research was done on the aspect of change proneness, so this investigation will throw some light on this unexplored area of research.

Objectives of the Study

- To understand the change proneness and psychological well being of elderly women living with family and living without family.
- To measure the change proneness and psychological well being of elderly living in urban and rural areas.
- To see the relationship between change proneness and psychological well being among elderly women.

Review of Literature

Na and Streim (2017) assessed the Psychosocial Well-Being Associated With Activity of Daily Living Stages Among Community-Dwelling Older Adults. Cross-sectional data from the National Social Life, Health, and Aging Project (N = 3,002) were analyzed in regression models and latent factor models. Results showed that elderly displayed negative social network. The study may aid clinicians and policy makers to understand the social and mental health needs of older adults at different ADL stages and provide well-planned social and mental health care.

Tandon (2017) assessed the psychological well-being among the elderly. The sample for this study comprised 120 elderly individuals (60 females and 60 males respectively) comprising of elderly living in home and old age home. Psychological well-being scale developed by Sisodia and Choudhary (1999) was used to assess the psychological well-being level. Significant difference in psychological level was found among the elderly living in the families and old age home. Rural women as compared to urban women had significantly lower scores on health rating, marital and life satisfaction. Rural women had less number of supports and life satisfaction with support. They reported more negative mood states and had higher scores on self-rating questionnaire. Females were found to be more on hopelessness and less satisfied with life as compared to males. Married older people were found to be low on hopelessness and high on life satisfaction as compared to widow / widower. Married females were high on alienation as compared to married males.

Yamada and Teerawichitchainan (2015) examined the relationship between living arrangements and psychological well-being of the older adults. 2,225 adults aged 60 were taken for the study. Results revealed that changes in living arrangements have resulted in significant differences in psychological well-being among the older adults. The findings point to the need for attention to the mental health of elderly parents left behind in less economically developed regions.

Srisailamaiah, Suresh and Reddy (2016) found out the mean difference between depression and psychological well-being among institutionalized and non- institutionalized elderly. The Geriatric depression Inventory (Holroyd & Clayton, 2000), and Psychological Wellbeing Scale (Bhogley & Prakash, 1995), were used on elderly population. For purposes of the present study, a total sample of 60 were taken out of which 30 were (60+ years) elderly people from old age homes and 30 were (60+ y ears) from non-institutionalized elderly. Result revealed significant differences in depression and psychological well-being with respect to institutionalized and non- institutionalized elderly. While co-relation between depression and psychological well-being reveals -0.68, negative correlation.

Amarya, Singh and Manisha Sabharwal (2015) found changes during aging and their association with malnutrition. Results revealed that due to changing socioeconomic environment, elderly people are often left alone to fend for themselves to maintain their health, which may interfere with the maintenance of a good nutritional status.

Chong et al (2015) explored psychosocial well-being of the elderly. Results postulate that different groups of elderly form friendships and participate in activities in both formal social service centers and informal public spaces. While the elderly residents are generally satisfied with physical infrastructure, a comprehensive, integrated urban design is further needed to facilitate physical activities, social interactions, and active aging in the elderly in order to enhance their psychosocial well-being.

Stephoe et al (2015) studied the relationship between psychological wellbeing, health and ageing. The relationship between physical health and subjective wellbeing is bidirectional. Older people suffering from illnesses such as coronary heart disease, arthritis and chronic lung disease show both raised levels of depressed mood and impaired hedonic and eudemonic wellbeing.

Methodology**Selection of area**

The area selected for the study comprised of elderly women from different households as well as 5 old age homes in the Chennai city. They are

- G.S Senior Citizens Home, CIT Nagar.
- Thavam Old Age Home, Washermanpet.
- Trinity Happy Home, Purasaiwalkam.
- Aruwe Old Age Home, Ayanavaram and
- Mercy Home, Halls Road, Kilpauk.

Selection of Sample

A sample of 120 elderly women was chosen with respect to place of residence and type of locality.

Selection of tools

To assess the change proneness, Development of Change Proneness Scale by Pratibha Sood and Shalini Bhogle (1997) was used and to assess the psychological well being Ryff's Psychological well being 18 item (1998) was used for the present study.

Results and Discussion**1. Change Proneness and Place of Residence****Table 1****Comparison of change proneness among elderly female living with and without family**

Variables	Gender	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	't'-value	Level of significance
Change proneness	Living with family	60	93.90	6.841	0.342	NS
	Living without family	60	93.47	7.04		

Note: NS-Not significant

The results in Table 1 reveals that there exist no significant difference in the change proneness between elderly female living with family and without family as the calculate t – value ($t = 0.342$) is less than the table value $t = 1.96$ at 5% level of significance, hence it is not significant.

2. Change Proneness and Type of Locality**Table 2****Comparison of change proneness among elderly female belonging to urban and rural areas**

Variables	Locality	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	't'-value	Level of significance
Change proneness	Urban	30	91.03	7.233	2.830	P<0.01
	Rural	30	95.90	6.036		

The results in Table 2 reveals that there exists a significant difference in the change proneness among elderly female belonging to urban and rural areas as the calculated 't' value ($t = 2.830$) is greater than the table value ($t=2.58$) at 1% level of significance. A further perusal of the table shows that change proneness was found to be more among elderly women in rural areas than urban areas. Elderly in rural areas are more attached to the family and they are willing to agree with the changes which they have to adapt in order to have good relationship with their family. Therefore change proneness was found to be more among the elders staying in rural area than those who stay in urban area.

3. Psychological Well-Being And Place of Residence

Table 3
Comparison of psychological well-being among elderly female living with and without family

Variables	Gender	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	't'-value	Level of significance
Psychological well-being	Living with family	60	70.03	10.433	0.485	NS
	Living without family	60	69.18	8.674		

Note: NS-Not significant

The results in Table 3 reveals that there exist no significant difference in the psychological well-being as the calculated 't' value ($t = 0.485$) is less than the table value $t = 1.96$ at 5% level of significance, hence it is not significant.

The above result is contradicted by the study conducted by Chamuah and Sankar (2017) who aimed to find the level of psychological well-being among elderly people. Result reveals that significant difference was found in psychological well-being with respect to place of residence.

4. Psychological Well-Being and Type of Locality

Table 4
Comparison of psychological well-being among elderly belonging to urban and rural areas

Variables	Locality	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	't'-value	Level of significance
Psychological well-being	Urban	60	72.25	9.308	3.136	P<0.01
	Rural	60	66.97	9.145		

The results in Table 4 reveals that there exists a significant difference in the psychological well-being between elderly belonging to urban and rural areas, as the calculated 't' value ($t = 3.136$) is greater than the table value ($t=2.58$), therefore it is found to be significant at 1% level of significance. Psychological well-being was found to be better among elderly living in urban area than the elderly staying in rural area.

The above result is supported by the study conducted by Yamadda and Teerawichitchainan (2015) who examined the relationship between living arrangements and psychological well-being of the older adults. Result reveals significant differences in psychological well-being among the older adults.

5. Change Proneness and Psychological Well-Being

Table 5
Relationship between change proneness and psychological well-being among elderly female

	Change Proneness	p-value
Psychological well-being	.275**	P < 0.01

Note: Significant at 1% level

The results in Table 5 reveals that there is a positive correlation between change proneness and psychological well-being among elderly female as the value of correlation was found to be .275.

This reveals that if a person is ready to change or alter her behaviour, attitudes, feelings and thoughts by being flexible rather than by restraining herself to be rigid she can have a cordial relationship with others which in turn will lead to having a better psychological well being.

Conclusion

- Elderly women living with family spend more time with friends and they are more social and active. To be a part of the circle they need to be ready to adapt changes than be rigid. Although minimal difference was found between both the groups change proneness was found to be slightly high among elderly women living with family.
- Change proneness was found to be more among elderly female staying in rural area than those who are staying in urban area. This reveals that elderly in rural area are more attached to family and are willing to adapt to change rather than being rigid.
- Elderly staying in urban area had better psychological well-being than those in rural areas as they had better facilities in urban areas.
- It was also revealed that there was found to be a relationship between psychological well-being and change proneness among the elderly female

Suggestions for Further Research

1. To compare the psychological well being and change proneness between male and female.
2. To have a comparative study between the sample from different types of family.
3. To compare it between the adults from different occupations.

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